

General Lorentz transformations and the simultaneity

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We have according to Jackson [3], equation (11.19):

$$c \cdot t' = x'_0 = \gamma \cdot (x_0 - \vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{x})$$

It is valid $\vec{\beta} = \frac{\vec{v}}{c}$ and $\gamma = (1 - \beta^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$. If we take into consideration $x_0 = c \cdot t$, then we obtain:

$$c \cdot t' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} \cdot (ct - \vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{x})$$

It follows:

$$t' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} \cdot \left(t - \frac{\vec{x} \cdot \vec{v}}{c^2} \right)$$

In this form the Lorentz transformation of time is written in Becker [1], exercise 10.1, p.305.

The Lorentz transformation of place by Jackson [3], equation (11.19):

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{x}' &= \vec{x} + \frac{\gamma - 1}{\beta^2} \cdot (\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{x}) \cdot \vec{\beta} - \gamma x_0 \vec{\beta} \\ &= \vec{x} + \frac{(1 - \beta^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} - 1}{\beta^2} \cdot (\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{x}) \cdot \vec{\beta} - \frac{ct \vec{\beta}}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} \\ &= \vec{x} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} \left(\frac{(\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{x}) \cdot \vec{\beta}}{\beta^2} - ct \vec{\beta} \right) - \frac{(\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{x}) \cdot \vec{\beta}}{\beta^2} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Now we use the identity:

$$\frac{(\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{x}) \cdot \vec{\beta}}{\beta^2} = \frac{(\vec{v} \cdot \vec{x}) \cdot \frac{\vec{v}}{c^2}}{\frac{v^2}{c^2}} = \frac{(\vec{v} \cdot \vec{x}) \cdot \vec{v}}{v^2} \tag{2}$$

With that:

$$\vec{x}' = \vec{x} + \frac{\vec{v}}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} \cdot \left(\frac{\vec{v} \cdot \vec{x}}{v^2} - t \right) - \frac{(\vec{v} \cdot \vec{x}) \cdot \vec{v}}{v^2} \tag{3}$$

This is equal to the form in Becker [1], exercise 10.1 p.305.

The Lorentz transformations of time in Schröder [4] (chapter 3.4, p.33, equation 8) and Becker [1], exercise 10.1, p.305 are the same.

From equation (1) we get

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{x}' &= \vec{x} + (\gamma - 1) \cdot \frac{(\vec{x}\vec{v}) \cdot \vec{v}}{v^2} - \gamma ct \cdot \frac{\vec{v}}{c} \\ &= \vec{x} + (\gamma - 1) \cdot \frac{(\vec{x}\vec{v}) \cdot \vec{v}}{v^2} - \gamma \vec{v}t\end{aligned}$$

by using $x_0 = ct$ and equation (2). This is the form in Schröder [4], see chapter 3.4, equation (8), p.33.

The general Lorentz transformations are the same in all 3 books.

Now we consider equation (3) for the special case $\vec{v} = (v, 0, 0)$ and $\vec{x} = (x, 0, 0)$:

$$\begin{aligned}x' &= x - \frac{vxv}{v^2} + \left(\frac{vx}{v^2} - t\right) \cdot \frac{v}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \\ &= \frac{x - vt}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}\end{aligned}$$

This is the known special Lorentz transformation. From the general Lorentz transformations of time in Becker [1], exercise 10.1, p.305 and Schröder [4] (chapter 3.4 at (8), p.33) follows by the same specialization the known special Lorentz transformation of time:

$$t' = \frac{t - \frac{vx}{c^2}}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}$$

With equation (3) we get for $|\vec{v}| \ll c$ and $|\vec{\beta}| \ll 1$:

$$\vec{x}' \approx \vec{x} - \frac{(\vec{x}\vec{v}) \cdot \vec{v}}{v^2} + \left(\frac{\vec{x}\vec{v}}{v^2} - t\right) \cdot \vec{v}$$

With that:

$$\vec{x}' \approx \vec{x} - t\vec{v}$$

From the Lorentz transformation of time (see Becker [1], exercise 10.1, p.305)

$$t' = \frac{t - \frac{\vec{x}\vec{v}}{c^2}}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}$$

we obtain for $|\vec{v}| \ll c$ and $|\vec{\beta}| \ll 1$:

$$t' \approx t$$

Now we view the problem of simultaneity of two vectors $\vec{x}_1$ and $\vec{x}_2$ from R^3 . It is valid:

$$t'_1 = \frac{t_1 - \frac{\vec{x}_1 \cdot \vec{v}}{c^2}}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} \quad t'_2 = \frac{t_2 - \frac{\vec{x}_2 \cdot \vec{v}}{c^2}}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}$$

The case $t_1 = t_2$ and $\vec{x}_1 = \vec{x}_2$, it follows:

$$t'_1 = t'_2$$

The case $t_1 = t_2$ and $\vec{x}_1 \neq \vec{x}_2$:

$$t'_1 - t'_2 = \frac{(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1) \cdot \vec{v}}{c^2 \cdot \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}$$

With that $t'_1 \neq t'_2$, for $|\vec{v}| \ll c$ it is valid $t'_1 \approx t'_2$.

References

- [1] Becker/Sauter "Theorie der Elektrizität", volume 1, Teubner Verlag, Stuttgart, 21.edition 1973
- [2] Harald Schröder "Particular problems of special relativity theory", Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002
- [3] John David Jackson "Klassische Elektrodynamik", de Gruyter Verlag, Berlin 1981
- [4] Ulrich Schröder "Spezielle Relativitätstheorie", Verlag Harri Deutsch, 2.edition, Frankfurt on the Main 1987